

Received: 01 January 2025 • Revised: 24 February 2025 • Accepted: 15 March 2025

Research

doi: 10.22034/jcema.2025.527093.1160

Study on Cross Girder to Rail Bearer Connections of Plate Girder Bridges in Sri Lanka Railways

Vanushan Kunanathan *, Kamal Karunananda

Department of Civil Engineering, The Open University of Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka.

*Correspondence should be addressed to Vanushan Kunanathan, Department of Civil Engineering, The Open University of Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka. ; Email: s20001664@ousl.lk

ABSTRACT

The connection between the cross girder and the rail bearer stands as one of the most critical structural details of plate girder bridges in Sri Lanka railways. Despite numerous modifications and advancements implemented by Sri Lankan railway engineers over time, this connection remains a repeated point of failure. This paper examines the underlying causes of these failures, in a plate girder railway bridge which is located in the coastal railway line of Sri Lanka, through numerical modelling and experimental validation. A global finite element model of the bridge was developed using SAP2000 V.23 to analyze the overall structural behavior, while a detailed local finite element model of the cross girder-rail bearer connection was developed in Abaqus V.6.14 to capture localized stress distributions and the failure mechanisms. To validate the numerical findings, vibration analysis was performed using smartphone-based measurements, where natural frequencies extracted from experimental data were compared with numerical predictions. The results of the numerical simulation indicate that the connecting plate in the cross girder-rail bearer connection is the most critical component in the selected bridge. Stress Triaxiality Factor (STF) analysis revealed that the plate undergoes high triaxial tensile stress states, particularly at its central region, indicating a high vulnerability to brittle failure with void growth. These results highlight the necessity of strengthening the connecting plate of the cross girder to rail bearer connection to enhance the structural integrity and the overall durability of the plate girder bridges.

Keywords: cross girder to rail bearer connection, plate girder, Railways, finite element modelling, smartphone sensor

Copyright © 2025, Vanushan Kunanathan. This is an open access paper distributed under the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). [Journal of Civil Engineering and Materials Application](https://doi.org/10.22034/jcema.2025.527093.1160) is published by [ISNet](https://www.isnet.org/); Journal p-ISSN 2676-332X; Journal e-ISSN 2588-2880.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sri Lanka has an extensive railway network of around 1350 bridges and culverts, which serves as the backbone of the nation's transportation system. According to the bridge register of Sri Lanka Railways (formerly, Ceylon Government Railway-CGR), More than 90% bridges are made of steel, highlighting the predominant use of steel in railway

bridge construction in Sri Lanka, possibly due to its high strength-to-weight ratio, components are pre-fabricated in factories and are quickly assembled on-site, and good fatigue resistance than concrete [1]. Now, the Sri Lanka railway network consists of 9 major lines with a total length of about 1262 km covering all 09 provinces of the country as

mentioned in [Table 1](#). The coastal line of Sri Lanka Railways is about 158 km in length, from Colombo (Maradana) to Beliatta and runs on the lower part of the west coast of the country [\[2\]](#). This line was the second railway line in Sri Lanka and was opened in 1894 by the British colonial government after the Colombo–Badulla Main Line [\[3\]](#), [\[4\]](#). Currently, it consists of 61 steel bridges. Many of these bridges were constructed in the 20th century and are still in

service, exceeding 50 years of life [\[5\]](#). However, with increasing train loads (magnitude and frequency) and the natural effects of aging, most of the steel railway bridges have started to deteriorate their condition, and even cracks have formed in some of the bridge members. [Table 1](#) summarizes the lengths and number of bridges along each railway line.

Table 1. Details of major railway lines in Sri Lanka

Line no.	Line	Length (km)	No. of bridges
1	Mainline (Colombo–Badulla)	291	159
2	Northern line (Polgahawela–Kankesanthurai)	339	352
3	Batticaloa line (Maho–Batticaloa)	212	119
4	Puttalam line (Ragama–Puttalam)	133	76
5	Coastal line (Maradana–Matara)	158	61
6	Trincomalee line (Gal Oya–Trincomalee)	70	46
7	KV line (Colombo fort–Avissawella)	60	42
8	Matale line (Peradeniya - Matale)	34	21
9	Mannar line (Madawachchiya - Thalaimannar)	106	63

A critical element in bridge stability is the cross girder to rail bearer connection (CG-RB). The rail bearers are placed parallel to the main girders right below the rails, and span between adjacent cross-girders with typical spans from 3m to 5m. These members are assumed to be simply supported or continuous, depending on their connections to cross girder. Further, the rail bearers carry the weight of rails, fastenings, the weight of sleepers, and their self-weight. The cross-girder spans right angles to the main girders and carries the weight of rails, fastenings, weight of sleepers, weight of rail bearers, and its self-weight. The cross girders are subjected to maximum live load and impact load when both the adjacent rail bearers are loaded.

In this study, a plate girder bridge in the coastal railway line was visually inspected, and defects were identified. [Figure 1](#) illustrates the key structural components of a typical plate girder railway bridge, including the main girders, cross girders, rail bearers, sway bracings, and wind bracings. These components work together to distribute loads from train traffic and maintain the bridge's lateral and longitudinal stability. As seen in [Figure 2](#), the connecting plate shows visible signs of excessive corrosion and material loss. This degradation is common in coastal environments and significantly weakens the structural integrity of the CG-RB connection. Frequent replacement of this component has been necessary during routine maintenance.

Figure 1. Components of a plate girder railway bridge

Figure 2. Corroded connecting plate removed from the bridge

Due to the bridge location on the coastline, prolonged exposure to the saline atmosphere makes corrosion an unavoidable form of degradation. [Figure 3](#) illustrates typical failure modes such as corrosion-induced section loss and cracking in the

CG-RB members. These visible defects emphasize the need for stress-based finite element analysis and justify the selection of this region for both local and global modeling efforts.

Figure 3. Corrosion and cracks in the members of CG-RB connection

The dynamic interaction between railway loads and bridge structures induces significantly higher stress than that estimated through static analysis alone, necessitating the application of dynamic amplification factors to accurately represent service conditions [\[2\]](#), [\[6\]](#). Stress concentrations commonly localize at critical junctions, particularly where cross girders connect to rail bearers or main girders, making these regions highly susceptible to fatigue cracking [\[7\]](#), [\[8\]](#). The three-dimensional behavior of plate girder bridges plays a crucial role in the development of these local stresses, as demonstrated through finite element modelling and empirical measurements, which revealed that fatigue cracks frequently initiate at cross-girder to rail bearer connections [\[8\]](#).

Continuity of rail bearers across cross girders can significantly reduce mid-span bending moments by allowing more effective load redistribution and enabling the rail bearers to function as continuous beams. Additionally, the structural behavior of plate

girders is influenced more by axle spacing than axle load magnitude, emphasizing the importance of span configuration in bridge response [\[9\]](#). Studies incorporating static and dynamic testing on bridges with high axle loads have shown that a considerable portion of longitudinal forces, nearly 50% is transferred to the girders, confirming their critical role in load-bearing behavior under train-induced loading conditions [\[10\]](#).

Vibrations induced by moving trains, braking actions, and track irregularities affect the performance, durability, and serviceability of railway bridges, with dynamic responses being highly sensitive to parameters such as span length, damping, boundary conditions, and material stiffness [\[11\]](#), [\[12\]](#). Resonance effects are of particular concern, as they arise when train loading frequencies coincide with the natural frequency of the bridge, potentially leading to excessive vibrations [\[11\]](#). Past research studies indicate that vehicle speed and axle configuration significantly influence vibration

amplitudes, while stiffer or heavier bridges tend to experience lower peak accelerations and delayed resonance responses. The use of analytical and experimental methods, especially finite element modelling validated by field measurements, remains essential for accurately predicting bridge performance under dynamic conditions and informing effective design and maintenance strategies [12], [2], [13].

In recent years, the integration of mobile technology into civil engineering practice has opened new pathways for cost-effective structural health monitoring (SHM). Smartphones, equipped with micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS) accelerometers, have emerged as practical tools for capturing structural vibration data. These devices are increasingly being used for validating finite element models (FEMs) and assessing the dynamic performance of structures under service conditions. Their portability, affordability, and capability to capture structural vibrations, particularly when used in direct contact with the structure, make them particularly suitable for preliminary investigations, field-based monitoring, and educational applications, especially in scenarios where traditional instrumentation is either unavailable or impractical [14].

While limitations such as noise interference, low sampling rates, and reduced sensitivity at high frequencies can affect data fidelity, the convenience

and affordability of smartphone-based sensing make it a viable alternative in scenarios where traditional sensors are impractical or prohibitively expensive. These devices support both contact-based methods and non-contact approaches, such as video-based motion tracking, enabling diverse applications ranging from laboratory experiments to in-field monitoring [14]. Furthermore, the vehicle-bridge interaction (VBI) technique, which interprets vertical accelerations of a moving vehicle to estimate a bridge's dynamic properties, has been effectively implemented using smartphones alongside standard sensors [15]. This approach enables the estimation of natural frequencies and offers a non-intrusive means of assessing structural health. Recent studies have shown that networks of smartphones can be deployed on long-span bridges to extract modal frequencies and mode shapes with reasonable accuracy [16]. These advancements affirm the growing potential of smartphones in dynamic structural assessment, especially in applications demanding mobility, affordability, and rapid deployment.

This study aims to identify the critical structural members of the bridge through numerical modeling and to validate the developed model using experimental data. Validation is intended to be achieved by conducting a smartphone-based vibration analysis of the bridge under live load conditions.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology followed to achieve the aim of this study is mentioned in detail below.

1. Literature review of past publications on the railway bridges along the coastline and discussions with Sri Lankan Railway personnel.
2. Conduct a field visit to visually inspect and assess the current condition of the bridge.
 - Identify the defects and perform an elementary survey to measure the dimensions of the members.
 - Observe the types of locomotives in operation on this bridge and find out the weight of each locomotive.
 - Collecting material samples for experimental evaluation.
3. Conducting tests to identify the mechanical properties of the material used for different bridge members.
 - Mechanical properties are yield strength, ultimate tensile strength, and modulus of elasticity
4. Develop a global numerical model of the bridge using SAP2000 V.23 software.
 - Identify the most critical cross girder to rail bearer connection of the bridge
5. Validating the numerical model using smartphone-based vibration analysis.
 - Measure acceleration data from the bridge using a smartphone under the live load conditions.
 - Calculate the natural frequency from the measured acceleration data and compare it with the natural frequency obtained from the numerical model to assess its accuracy.
6. Develop a local model of the critical connection using Abaqus V.6.14 software.

- Determine the stresses on the various elements at the cross girder–rail bearer

connection and identify the most critical member.

7. Result analysis and interpretation.

2.1. Material Testing

Beginning in the late 1990s, high-strength structural steels such as S355 have been progressively adopted as standard materials in bridge construction due to their superior mechanical properties and enhanced performance under load [17], [18]. Past research study on SLR bridges has highlighted that S355 steel has been used for bridge constructions since 2004 [19]. Material testing conducted [7] on a coastal railway bridge built during the same period with the

same type of steel supports this information. To validate this, material samples were obtained from the bridge during routine maintenance. A connecting plate having a thickness of 12mm was tested using a digital Rockwell hardness tester with ASTM E18-15 standards as shown in Figure 4. The average hardness measured was HRB 61.3, indicating the steel is likely S355.

Figure 4. Specimen on digital Rockwell hardness testing machine

The mechanical properties of the steel used in the bridge are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of S355 steel [7]

Mechanical Properties	Value
Yield strength (MPa)	355
Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	433
Strain at break (mm/mm)	0.36
Fracture strength (MPa)	287

2.2. Finite element modelling of the bridge (Global numerical model)

The selected Panadura railway bridge is a semi through continuous plate girder bridge, consisting of a total length of 194.24 m with four equal spans and consists of various members such as main girders, cross girders, rail bearers, sway bracings, and wind

bracings. It is supported on the piers using elastomeric bearings. Therefore, one end support was fixed while other supports were pin-supported considering the continuity of the bridge. (Figure 5).

Figure 5. 3D bridge model developed using SAP2000 software

2.3. Assigned loads

The M11 is the heaviest locomotive operating on this bridge, with a total weight of 120 tons distributed across six axles. Therefore, M11 was selected to determine the critical cross girder to rail bearer connection and the impact loads from the passenger compartments are negligible when compared with the engine. The model was run in 19 various load combinations when the train was on the bridge.

Due to the dynamic effects associated with moving trains, the actual service load on the bridge would be higher than the static

load. Therefore, a dynamic factor of 1.5 was applied to the static load to estimate the service load [6]. The load configuration assumes that the total weight is transmitted from the axles through the wheels and ultimately to the rail bearers. Additionally, the force exerted by each wheel was applied as a point load, as shown in Figure 6, with axle spacing provided in millimeters. Accurate representation of axle spacing and load magnitude is essential for determining critical loading scenarios and stress concentrations in bridge components.

Figure 6. Load geometry of M11 locomotive

Figure 7 identifies the regions experiencing the maximum stress on the bridge for different load combinations. These stress patterns were correlated

with data in Table 3, which lists axial forces at the CG-RB connection.

Figure 7. Maximum Von-Mises stress location on the bridge

The maximum stress corresponding to each loading case and load combination was extracted and tabulated in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Maximum stress on the bridge with location

Location of Locomotive (m)	Axial load at the CG-RB connection (kN)		
	1.4 Gk + 1.6 Qk	Gk + 1.5 Qk	Gk + Qk
0	-39.1	-7.4	-24.8
10	66.9	58.7	43.5
20	83.8	72.7	54.8
30	69.8	60.5	45.6
40	-15.3	-11.2	-10.9
50	21.6	20.7	13.3
60	40.6	36.9	25.8
70	51.1	47.2	32.2
80	-21	-18	-13.8
90	-32.2	-28.4	-20.8
100	38.3	35.4	24.2
110	70.9	65.4	44.8
120	51	47	32
130	-33.9	-29.2	-22.2
140	-46.7	-40.4	-30.5
150	33.2	31	20.8
160	105.2	93.3	68.1
170	58.2	50.1	38.1
180	58.1	48.7	38.6

It is clear from [Table 3](#), that the maximum stress occurs when the locomotive is positioned at 160 m and the natural frequency obtained from the finite element bridge model was 0.161 Hz. Therefore,

2.4. Vibration analysis

In this study, vibration measurements were obtained using smartphones equipped with the ‘Phyphox’ application, which utilizes the built-in accelerometer to record acceleration data. Four measurement locations were strategically selected on the bridge based on anticipated zones of significant vibration, enabling a comprehensive assessment of the structural response during testing.

these corresponding stress values can be used to develop the local modelling of the critical CG-RB connection.

The selected test locations are illustrated in [Figures 8, 9 and 10](#). [Figures 9 and 10](#) illustrate the physical setup of smartphones fixed on the rail bearer and cross girder, respectively. The devices were mounted in direct contact with the bridge members using high power double tape, ensuring minimal movement and accurate vibration capture during train passage.

Figure 8. Plan view of test locations

Figure 9. Smartphone fixed on Rail bearer

Figure 10. Smartphone fixed on cross girder

The test configurations are shown in [Table 4](#) below.

Table 4. Test configurations

Span	Locomotive class	Location	Member	Smartphone
Span 1	S-8	A	Main girder	iPhone 6s+
		B	Rail bearer 1	iPhone 8
Span 2	M-4	C	Cross girder	iPhone 8
		D	Rail bearer 2	iPhone 6s+

Measurements were recorded in three directions: x, y, and z as shown in [Figures 11, 12, 13](#) and [14](#). The data for each direction were collected over time,

resulting in acceleration vs. time graphs that display the variation in acceleration as the vibrations occurred.

Figure 11. Acceleration vs time graph for location A

Figure 12. Acceleration vs time graph for location B

Figure 13. Acceleration vs time graph for location C

Figure 14. Acceleration vs time graph for location D

The power spectral density (PSD) was determined by applying the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to the acceleration data, and the PSD vs. frequency was generated in MATLAB Online software. The

dominant frequency in the plot is the natural frequency of the bridge. The PSD vs frequency plots for the locations A, B, C and D are shown in [Figures 15, 16, 17, and 18](#), respectively.

Figure 15. PSD vs frequency graph for location A

Figure 16. PSD vs frequency graph for location B

Figure 17. PSD vs frequency graph for location C

Figure 18. PSD vs frequency graph for location D

The average natural frequency recorded was 0.1945 Hz, and this value was used to validate the global

numerical model.

2.5. Finite element modelling of the critical connection (Local numerical model)

The identified critical CG-RB connection was modelled and the corresponding loads and boundary conditions extracted from global analysis were applied to the model. Abaqus V.16.4 software was used for this local modelling and simulation of the connection. The model was run for various load cases to simulate the actual behavior of the

connection. [Figure 19](#) shows the Abaqus model of the CG-RB connection. All relevant structural details such as bolt arrangements, gusset plates, connecting plates, and support constraints were included.

Figure 19. Final assembly of the CG-RB connection

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Validation of global models

The natural frequency obtained from the SAP2000 bridge model was 0.161 Hz, while the average actual value from the smartphone-based vibration test was 0.1945 Hz, showing a slight discrepancy. This difference can be attributed mainly to the presence of severe corrosion in the real bridge, which is challenging to accurately model in finite element software due to the varying extent of section reduction across different locations. With limited facilities, it is also difficult to quantify this

deterioration precisely. Incorporating the actual corrosion levels into the model would likely predict a natural frequency closer to the measured value. Additionally, the smartphone-based test method itself has limitations in accuracy as well. Despite these factors, the numerical results are still reasonably close to the actual behavior, providing sufficient evidence to consider the model as validated.

3.2. Results of local numerical model

The local finite element model (FEM) was developed for the 30th CG-RB connection when the locomotive is at 160m from the Panadura station end. The respective loads and boundary conditions were applied. The model was run for four different

load cases to simulate the actual behavior of the connection. The analysis has shown that the most critical elements are the connecting plates, rail bearers and the gusset plates, indicating the higher stress concentration ([Table 5](#)).

Table 5. Maximum Von–Mises stress on members

Load case	Maximum stress (MPa)			
	Cross girder	Gusset plate	Connecting plate	Rail bearer
Gk only	9.4	14.16	15.44	13.56
Gk + Qk	37.6	84.09	84.94	78.09
Gk + 1.5Qk	51.5	117.29	118.71	108.65
1.4 Gk + 1.6 Qk	55.9	128.57	130.41	119.03

3.3. Comparison of numerical results with actual defects on the bridge

[Figure 20](#) highlights the FEA-predicted deformation, which shows high stress regions around bolt holes. In contrast, [Figure 21](#) displays the

actual deformed plate with failure concentrated in the central zone.

Figure 20. Finite element analysis of the connecting plate

Figure 21. Actual deformation of removed connecting plate

Although the results from local finite element model and the observed defects show some agreement, there is a notable difference in the failure patterns. While the finite element analysis (FEA) indicates high stress concentrations around the bolt holes, the actual plate failures occur in the central region. This suggests that stress magnitude alone, as predicted by Abaqus, might not fully capture the failure initiation mechanism in this scenario. To better understand this, calculating the stress triaxiality factor (STF) is

crucial for identifying the most critical locations for failure, as STF accounts for the multi-axial stress state and its influence on ductile fracture. A potential drawback of the Abaqus analysis is its limitation in accurately predicting the failure location based solely on stress magnitude, highlighting the need for more advanced failure criteria, such as those incorporating stress triaxiality, to improve the correlation between FEA predictions and real-world failure behavior.

3.4. Stress triaxiality factor (STF)

Stress triaxiality is a measure of the state of stress at a point in a material and is defined as the ratio of hydrostatic stress to the Von Mises stress. It plays a crucial role in understanding the material's behavior, especially when it comes to ductile failure.

After obtaining stress results for the critical members from Abaqus, the stress triaxiality factor was calculated using equation 1 to further analyze and optimize the design, ensuring it can withstand potential failure modes.

$$STF(\eta) = \sigma_h / \sigma_v \quad (\text{Eq 1})$$

where:

- σ_h is the hydrostatic stress, calculated as $(\sigma_I + \sigma_{II} + \sigma_{III})/3$
- σ_v is the von Mises stress

$$\sigma_v = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}[(\sigma_I - \sigma_{II})^2 + (\sigma_{II} - \sigma_{III})^2 + (\sigma_{III} - \sigma_I)^2]} \quad (\text{Eq 2})$$

Here,

- σ_I represents the first principal stress.
- σ_{II} represents the second principal stress.
- σ_{III} represents the third principal stress.

To evaluate the potential for fracture initiation in the connecting plate under the applied loading, a detailed Stress Triaxiality Factor (STF) analysis was conducted. The STF, a dimensionless parameter indicative of the hydrostatic stress state relative to the equivalent stress as stated in equation 1, was calculated at nineteen distinct locations on the plate (Figure 22).

Figure 22. STF calculated locations

These locations included three specific points on the plate body, labelled A, B, and C, strategically positioned to capture the overall stress distribution. Additionally, sixteen points (numbered 1 to 16) were selected around the bolt holes, recognizing these regions as potential stress concentration zones and likely sites for damage initiation. For each of these nineteen points, the three principal stresses (σ_I , σ_{II} , σ_{III}) and the Von Mises equivalent stress (σ_v) were extracted from the finite element analysis results

obtained using Abaqus V.6.14. These values were then utilized in Equation 1 to determine the STF at each point of interest.

The resulting STF values, along with the corresponding stress components, are summarized in Tables 6 and 7 for the plate body and around the bolt holes, respectively, providing a quantitative assessment of the stress state and its influence on the material's fracture behavior at these critical locations.

Table 6. STF values on the plate

Point	Von-Mises stress (Mpa)	σ_I	σ_{II}	σ_{III}	STF
A	61.2	65.4	9.3	0.05	0.41
B	70.4	70.4	-0.007	-0.1	0.33
C	53.5	52.3	0.06	-2.4	0.31

Table 7. STF values around the bolt holes

Point	Von-Mises stress (Mpa)	σ_I	σ_{II}	σ_{III}	STF
1	71.4	42.9	-0.3	-39.5	0.01
2	77.4	62.7	0.2	-23.8	0.17
3	88.1	78.9	0.12	-16.8	0.24
4	124.7	108.3	0.67	-28.3	0.22
5	125.5	113.5	0.4	-21.6	0.25
6	87.9	74.1	-0.25	-22.9	0.19
7	77.24	61.3	0.18	-25.5	0.16
8	72	43.1	-0.08	-40.04	0.01
9	73.1	35.7	-0.11	-48.4	-0.06
10	67.3	54.1	-0.28	-21.1	0.16
11	89.4	75.6	-0.35	-22.9	0.20
12	129.9	116.8	0.08	-23.04	0.24
13	129.7	116.7	0.1	-23.1	0.24
14	89.7	81.6	0.01	-14.4	0.25
15	67.8	54.3	-0.3	-21.5	0.16
16	71	36.7	0.14	-45.1	-0.04

According to the values from [Tables 6](#) and [7](#), the central region of the plate exhibited the highest STF value of approximately 0.41, which indicates a stress state in the transition zone between ductile and brittle failure mechanisms. However, due to the relatively low thickness of the plate (12 mm), the material response is expected to shift toward brittle failure. Brittle fracture under such conditions is

4. CONCLUSION

This research was aimed to study and improve the safety of plate girder railway bridges in the Sri Lankan railway system by focusing on the connection between cross girders and rail bearers (CG-RB). Through a combination of field investigations, finite element analysis, and vibration testing, the objectives of the study have been successfully achieved as the study has provided a comprehensive understanding of the structural behavior and critical vulnerabilities of the CG-RB connection.

Based on the results obtained from the numerical simulations and field observations, the following conclusions can be drawn. The study identified the connecting plate in the cross girder–rail bearer connection as the most critical component of the selected plate girder railway bridge. Finite element analysis revealed that the central region of the plate exhibits the highest stress triaxiality factor (STF \approx

typically driven by high triaxial tensile stresses that restrict plastic deformation and promote crack initiation and propagation. On the other hand, the bolt holes 1, 8, 9, and 16 have the lowest STF values (around 0 or negative) and are more likely to initiate shear failures. In contrast, the remaining bolt holes are subjected to higher tension, which may contribute to ductile failure.

0.41), indicating a failure stress state in the transition zone between ductile and brittle failure mechanisms. Further, there is a high susceptibility to brittle failure through void growth, especially considering the plate’s relatively small thickness of 12 mm. Field observations further confirmed that severe corrosion is concentrated at the centre of the plate, reducing its effective thickness and increasing its susceptibility to brittle fracture. Although bolt hole regions demonstrated moderate STF values (≈ 0.22 – 0.25) and are traditionally known as stress concentrators, no significant corrosion was observed near these areas in the actual structure. Therefore, the most critical and likely failure region is the corroded central part of the plate, where both high mechanical stress and advanced material deterioration coexist. This highlights the urgent need for strengthening or retrofitting the connecting plate

to enhance the durability and safety of the bridge connection.

In addition to the connecting plate, the gusset plates that connect the rail bearer to the cross girder were also found to experience significantly high stress levels in the finite element analysis. These gusset plates play a critical role in transferring loads between components, and any compromise in their integrity could adversely affect the overall performance of the connection. While this study

primarily focused on the connecting plate, field observations suggest that these gusset plates are also exposed to corrosion, particularly at their edges and weld regions. Therefore, a detailed analysis of these gusset plates, incorporating actual material deterioration due to corrosion, is essential in future work to ensure a more comprehensive understanding of the connection's behavior and to develop very effective maintenance or retrofitting strategies.

FUNDING/SUPPORT

Not mentioned any Funding/Support by authors.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank the Sri Lanka Railway Department for their assistance throughout this research. Specifically, for the support provided during the visual inspection and bridge testing, as well as for the materials supplied for the laboratory experiments.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author (s) declared no potential conflicts of interests with respect to the authorship and/or publication of this paper.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Wickramarathna U, Wijedasa R, Liyanagama J, Condition assessment and evaluation of the Narahenpita railway bridge. 2021. [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [2] Padmasiri HS, Punyawardhana GL, Limesha DK, Karunananda PA. Effect of Live Load Increment of Old Steel Railway Bridges in Sri Lanka. In International Conference on Sustainable Built Environment 2022 Nov 15 (pp. 3-15). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [3] Rampala BD, De Silva LS. History of the sri lanka government railway: b.d. rampala felicitation volume., 1991. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [4] History of Sri Lankan Railways, (accessed 17 July 2025). [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [5] CSRP | Colombo Suburban Railway Project - Sri Lanka, (accessed 7 May 2025). [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [6] Ranaweera MP, Aberuwan H, Herath KR, Maharoo AL, Siriwardane SA, Abesoorya AM. Assessment of Kelani railway bridge over Kelani river. Engineering Design Center, University of Peradeniya, Sri Lanka. 2002. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#);
- [7] Viththagan V, Wimalasiri RJ, Karunananda PA. Condition Assessment of the Critical Members of the Steel Bridges to Improve Reliability. In 8th International Symposium on Advances in Civil and Environmental Engineering Practices for Sustainable Development (ACEPS) 2021. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [8] OKURA I, YUBISUI M, HIRANO H, FUKUMOTO Y. Local stresses at cross beam connections of plate girder bridges. Doboku Gakkai Ronbunshu. 1988 Apr 20;1988(392):111-9. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [9] Philbrick Jr TW, Zodo GW, Schiff SD. Fatigue assessment of through plate girder railway bridges. Journal of Structural Engineering. 1995 Nov;121(11):1613-9. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [10] Srinivas V, Sasmal S, Banjara NK, Ramanjaneyulu K, Iyer NR. Health assessment of a plate girder railway bridge under increased axle loads. Journal of Bridge Engineering. 2013 Oct 1;18(10):969-79. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [11] Frýba L. A rough assessment of railway bridges for high speed trains. Engineering structures. 2001 May 1;23(5):548-56. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [12] Björklund L. Dynamic analysis of a railway bridge subjected to high speed trains. (2005, accessed 1 May 2025). [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [13] Gocál J, Vičan J, Jošt J. Real Stiffness and Fatigue Resistance of Stringer-to-Cross-Girder Connection of Riveted Steel Railway Bridges. Applied Sciences. 2023 Feb 10;13(4):2278. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [14] Riley C. Mobile Phone-Based Contact and Non-Contact Vibration Sensing for Structural Dynamics Teaching Laboratories. In 2023 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition 2023 Jun 25. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [15] Di Matteo A, Fiandaca D, Pirrotta A. Smartphone-based bridge monitoring through vehicle-bridge interaction: analysis and experimental assessment. Journal of Civil Structural Health Monitoring. 2022 Dec;12(6):1329-42. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [16] Ozer E, Purasinghe R, Feng MQ. Multi-output modal identification of landmark suspension bridges with distributed smartphone data: Golden Gate Bridge. Structural Control and Health Monitoring. 2020 Oct;27(10):e2576. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [17] Viththagan V, Wimalasiri RJ, Karunananda PA. Estimating Remaining Fatigue Life of Critical Members of Steel Railway Bridges using Fatigue Crack Growth Model. Engineer: Journal of the Institution of Engineers, Sri Lanka. 2023 Sep 25;56(3). [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [18] Bandara CS, Jayasinghe JA, Karunananda PA, Dissanayake UI. Metals used in old Bridges in Sri Lanka and the Effects of their Material Properties on Capacity Estimations. Engineer: Journal of the Institution of Engineers, Sri Lanka. 2017 Sep 10;50(3). [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)
- [19] Karunananda PAK, Karunarathna OGLK, Madusara HAKM. Life Assessment of High Strength Steel Bridges under Corrosion Attack. LAP Lambert Academic Publishers, 2023. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#); [\[View at Publisher\]](#)